

Finite element simulations of the electro-chemo-mechanical behavior of articular cartilage. Part I: theoretical formulation

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Abstract

Articular cartilage is a porous medium, reinforced by collagen fibers and saturated by an aqueous electrolyte. The presence of electrically charged macromolecules, the proteoglycans, leads to electro-chemo-mechanical interactions in the tissue which enhance its adaptation to physiological requests. In the present work, a new finite element formulation is presented and a finite element program is developed, with the purpose of numerically simulate the response of an articular cartilage sample to a combination of chemical and mechanical actions. The model considers the distinct physiological and mechanical roles of the fluid in the intrafibrillar and extrafibrillar compartments. As a new feature, the presence of the intrafibrillar fluid is taken into account in a straightforward manner based on experimental observations. Parametric identification and simulations of actual loading processes are described in part II of this paper.

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1. Introduction

Synovial joints are a specific group of joints in the human body that present a fibrous capsule filled by a fluid rich in nutrients (the synovial fluid) which nourishes a thin layer of articular cartilage that covers the extremities of the bones and provides frictionless movements in the joint [1],[2]. Articular cartilage is a highly specialized connective tissue, lacking nerves and blood vessels, characterized as a porous medium structured by collagen fibers (mostly of type II) and saturated by an electrolyte (representing 60% to 85% of the total volume of the tissue) with water as solvent and metallic ions as solutes [2-5]. Charged macromolecules, the proteoglycans (PG), intermingled with collagen fibers, give rise to electro-chemo-mechanical couplings that allow moderate deformation to take place and ensure an optimal adaptation of the tissue to physiological loads. Collagen and PGs are, thus, the main components of the extracellular matrix (ECM), responsible for the support of the stresses resulting from the forces in the joints and, together with water and dissolved inorganic salts, determine the complex behavior of the tissue that we wish to model in a macroscopic continuum framework. The cells present in the tissue (the chondrocytes) which are responsible for both the production and degradation of the ECM, being in this way in charge for its maintenance and repair, represent just 2% to 10% of the adult cartilage volume [3],[4].

Collagen is a fundamental protein with the tropocollagen molecule as its basic unit. Each tropocollagen unit is composed by three polypeptide chains that coil around each other forming a triple helix. The subsequent polymerization of the tropocollagen molecules originates collagen fibrils that, when grouped together, create a collagen fiber. The triple helix configuration, in addition to the covalent cross links that can be formed between the fibrils, provide collagen and the tissue with its tensile (stiffness and strength) properties [4].

Proteoglycans are composed by a protein core attached to several glycosaminoglycan (GAG) chains, which may further aggregate through a non-covalent protein linkage to a hyaluronan (HA) molecule. According to its GAG composition, different types of proteoglycans may be found among the tissue; aggrecan, the most abundant one, is gifted with the greatest capability to interact with HA molecules through the link protein [3],[4]. The link protein provides stabilization to the PGs aggregation, contributing to the immobilization of PGs within the collagen network, which has a major importance in the normal function of articular cartilage [3]. Under physiologic conditions, the GAG chains are negatively charged due to the presence of sulfate and carboxyl groups and the high number of fixed negative charges

(the fixed charge density - FCD) causes electrostatic repulsive forces between these molecules. The existence of these forces plays an important role in the tissue compressive stiffness since, when a compressive force is applied, the repulsion between the PG molecules opposes the movement and, therefore, if the number of PGs in the cartilage tissue increases, the FCD and the compressive stiffness increase as well [3].

The system comprising the tissue and the synovial fluid tends to evolve in order to achieve chemical balance. For instance, if the salt concentration (*e.g.* NaCl, CaCl₂) in the synovial fluid increases (hypertonic solution), a higher amount of ionic species is attracted inside the tissue according to Donnan's osmotic effect. Inside the tissue, these counter-ions shield the electrostatic repulsive forces between PGs and, consequently, allow for a higher contractive deformation or, equivalently, a lower compressive stiffness of the tissue [3]. By the contrary, in the presence of a hypotonic surrounding medium, less cations will also be present inside the tissue, leading to higher repulsive forces between PGs, lower contractive deformations and higher compressive stiffness [6]. The chemical composition of the synovial fluid has, additionally, an impact on the level of swelling and hydration of the tissue. According to the osmotic effect, water tends to flow from a medium with lower concentration of ions to a medium with higher concentration. In this way, due to the fact that the PG molecule is negatively charged and counter-ions are always present inside the tissue, in the presence of a hypotonic surrounding medium, an osmotic flow is generated leading to the migration of water from the hypotonic region (outside the tissue) towards the hypertonic region (inside), contributing to the swelling of the tissue [7]. However, when the surrounding medium is hypertonic (with higher concentration of salt), the tissue loses water and shrinks [6].

The fluid part of cartilage is therefore a vital component of the tissue, since it is responsible not only for the exchange of nutrients and waste products between the chondrocytes and the synovial fluid in the joint, but it also plays an important role in defining the mechanical response of the cartilage due to the presence of dissolved inorganic free cations such as Na⁺ and Ca²⁺, which balance the proteoglycan negative charges. Within the cartilage tissue, water may be found, besides inside the cells, in two different locations: (a) in the intrafibrillar (IF) space, inside the collagen fibers (between the collagen fibrils) or (b) in the extrafibrillar (EF) space, outside the collagen fibers and covering the proteoglycan molecules. In both spaces, part of the water is free to move when some load (*e.g.* compressive force) is applied or due to the presence of an osmotic pressure [3,4,8].

As any other tissue of the body, during the natural aging process of life, the cartilage tissue may suffer modifications in the ECM, due to alterations in the normal function of the chondrocytes, that lose their full capacity to synthesize the ECM components [9], [10]. Osteoarthritis is a disease characterized by the loss of articular cartilage in the joints (decrease of its thickness) due to an unbalance between synthesis and degradation of the cartilage components (promotion of the cells' catabolic process over the anabolic), culminating in altered biomechanics. Therefore, the understanding and knowledge of the tissue behavior and its evolution through age is crucial in the improvement of prevention and treatment of the degenerative pathologies that may affect the cartilage tissue as well as in the development of novel engineered materials to be used in regenerative medicine.

Over the past years, several chemo-mechanical models have been proposed to capture various aspects of articular cartilage response. In a work conducted by Mow *et al.* [11], the cartilage tissue was considered as a combination of a fluid and a solid phase. In such model, the collagen matrix, along with the proteoglycans, compose the solid phase of a matrix considered to be a porous, permeable medium. The fluid phase accounted for the interstitial fluid, being both phases incompressible. The triphasic model, proposed by Lai *et al.* [12], is an extension of the latter biphasic model, where the cartilage tissue is now decomposed into three phases: an incompressible interstitial fluid phase, accounting for the presence of water, an ionic phase composed by the ionic species Na⁺ and Cl⁻ (addition relatively to the biphasic model), and an incompressible solid phase, comprising the collagen and proteoglycan molecules of the porous-permeable ECM. The model was later generalized to include multi-electrolytes [13].

According to the experimental observations by Maroudas *et al.* [8], the presence of water in two distinct compartments of the tissue is significant for the mechanical aspects of its response. Along this perspective, Huyghe [14] and Loret and Simões [15-17] proposed a three phase electro-chemo-mechanical model with one solid and two fluid phases. In the latter model, the EF fluid phase included the EF water, the charged proteoglycans and dissolved ions, while the IF fluid phase was constituted by the IF water along with dissolved salts. The collagen fibers are the components of the solid phase. Water and ions of the IF phase have first to transfer through the collagen wall to reach the EF phase, being the latter the one that communicates with the external environment. In order to model the exchanges of mass between the two fluid phases and between the EF compartment and the surrounding medium, equations of mass transfer, together with the generalized diffusion equations developed in [18], were implemented in the simulation of the mechanical response of the tissue using the finite element method [19]. The consideration in these models of two fluid phases may be particularly important when studying osteoarthritis since collagen fibers, which become damaged in a osteoarthritic

cartilage, act in the model like membranes between these two compartments. Although quite complete, the model by Loix *et al.* [19] requires the definition of several material parameters that cannot be obtained from the existing experimental data, including the characteristic transfer times between the IF and EF phases (the mass transfer between phases is not instantaneous) and the parameters related to the difference of the pressure of water in these phases. Moreover, with this model, the authors were not able to replicate the experimental results by Eisenberg and Grodzinsky [6]. Nonetheless, the model used in [19] introduces, for the first time, the notion of *fictitious bath* or *equilibrium bath* that is used to define the articular cartilage mechanical parameters.

The finite element formulation proposed in this paper follows the framework of the model by Loix *et al.* [19], that is, a three phase model is also considered, with one solid phase and two fluid phases, accounting for the presence of two water compartments (EF and IF phases). However, as new features of the present formulation: 1) the electro-chemo-mechanical constitutive law used in this work is defined in [20], which is different from the one used by Loix *et al.* [19] and 2) the contribution of the IF phase to the simulations is considered in a different and simplified way, not requiring the definition of IF material parameters and functions. In fact, according to Bassler *et al.* [21], during a compression test in a specimen extracted from the hip, the percentage of IF water varied from 23.32% to 27.80% of the total amount of water, in all the stages of the test. Thus, a fixed value of 25% is considered in this work for the percentage of IF water with respect to the total amount of water, and consequently, the percentage attributed to the EF part is the remaining 75%. Exchange of mass (ions and water) between the EF phase and the environment surrounding the tissue (bath/synovial fluid) through boundary membranes, always guaranteeing the equilibrium at the interface between the exterior and interior of the tissue, is taken into account as well as diffusion of the ionic species within the EF phase. Only the presence of Na^+ and Cl^- is considered in this model since NaCl is the most abundant salt in the tissue [3]. As a simplification over [15-17] and [19], exchange of ions between the two fluid phases, although existing, is not modelled and, therefore, there is no access to the values of the masses of the IF ionic species. Proteoglycans, being macromolecules, do not pass through the membranes, thus they only exist in the EF phase.

Following this formulation, a finite element program is developed in MATLAB environment with the purpose of numerically simulate the response of an articular cartilage sample to a combination of chemical and mechanical actions. Parametric identification and simulations of actual loading processes are described in part II of this paper.

2. Field and constitutive equations

2.1. Mass and volume measures

The cartilage sample is a multi-phase tissue, being as well a multi-species mixture, composed by water (w), sodium (Na^+), chloride (Cl^-), among others. In this work, two distinct phases will be directly modelled: the EF fluid phase, $E = \{w, PG, Cl^-, Na^+\}$, and the solid phase, composed by the cartilage fibers, $S = \{c\}$. The EF phase may be further divided in two distinct subsets: one composed by the mobile species, $E^{mo} = \{w, Cl^-, Na^+\}$, and one composed only by the ionic species, $E^{ions} = \{Cl^-, Na^+\}$.

In this way, two types of constitutive equations are required to describe the tissue behavior: electro-chemo-mechanical equations, which account for deformation, and generalized diffusion equations, describing the flow of the ionic species and water through the extrafibrillar phase.

During the development of the field and constitutive equations, that will be conducted further ahead, several mass and volume quantities in the EF phase will be used, which need therefore to be defined *a priori*. The current volume, the current mass and the current number of moles of the species k in the EF phase will be denoted as V_{kE} , M_{kE} and N_{kE} , respectively. Considering V_0 the initial volume of the porous medium, and V and V_E the current total and EF volumes, several other entities related to the species k in this phase may be defined:

- some are intrinsic, like the intrinsic density $\rho_k = M_{kE}/V_{kE}$, the molar volume $\hat{v}_k = V_{kE}/N_{kE}$ and the molar mass $\hat{m}_k = M_{kE}/N_{kE}$ related by $\rho_k = \hat{m}_k / \hat{v}_k$;
- some refer to the current volume, like the volume fraction $n^{kE} = V_{kE}/V$ and the apparent density $\rho^{kE} = n^{kE} \rho_k = M_{kE}/V$;
- some refer to the initial volume, like the mass content $m^{kE} = M_{kE}/V_0$, the volume content $v^{kE} = V_{kE}/V_0 = m^{kE}/\rho_k$ and the molar content $\mathcal{N}_{kE} = N_{kE}/V_0$;
- and some are defined in the EF phase, like the molar concentration $c_{kE} = N_{kE}/V_E$ and the molar fraction $x_{kE} = N_k / \sum_k N_{kE}$.

All the entities described above can also be obtained for the EF phase as a whole by summing the contributions of all the species: volume content $v^E = \sum_k v^{kE}$, volume fraction $n^E = \sum_k n^{kE}$, total number of moles $N_E = \sum_k N_{kE}$ and molar content $\mathcal{N}_E = \sum_k \mathcal{N}_{kE} = N_E/V_0$.

2.2. Mass and momentum balances

The mass balance equation of mobile EF species (water and ionic species) can be written as [22]

$$\frac{dm^{kE}}{dt} + \operatorname{div} \mathbf{M}_{kE} = 0, \quad k \in E^{mo}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{M}_{kE}$ is the mass flux of the species through the solid skeleton defined as

$$\rho_k^{-1} \mathbf{M}_{kE} = n_{kE} (\mathbf{v}_{kE} - \mathbf{v}_S), \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{kE}$ is the velocity of species k and $\mathbf{v}_S$ is the solid skeleton velocity. Eq.(1) reflects the fact that the change of mass of the fluid phase species k is due to the mass exchange with the surroundings.

Dividing Eq.(1) by ρ_k , we obtain

$$\frac{dv^{kE}}{dt} + \operatorname{div} \mathbf{J}_{kE} = 0, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_{kE}$ is the species volume flux through the solid skeleton

$$\mathbf{J}_{kE} = \rho_k^{-1} \mathbf{M}_{kE} = n_{kE} (\mathbf{v}_{kE} - \mathbf{v}_S). \quad (4)$$

Assuming that the solid skeleton and all the EF species are incompressible, the change of volume of the tissue is symmetric to the change of the volume of the fluid phase due to diffusion, that is

$$\operatorname{div} \mathbf{v}_S + \operatorname{div} \mathbf{J}_E = \mathbf{0}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_E = \sum_{k \in E} \mathbf{J}_{kE}$, which is obtained summing up Eq.(4) for all the EF species and assuming that the velocity of the proteoglycans is equal to the solid phase velocity.

Neglecting body forces and dynamic effects, the balance of momentum equation is

$$\operatorname{div} \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (6)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the total Cauchy stress tensor.

2.3. The global structure of the constitutive equations

The global structure of the constitutive equations was previously developed, in a thermodynamic framework, in [23]. In such framework, the Clausius-Duhem inequality, neglecting thermal effects and considering the contribution of just one fluid phase (in this work the IF phase is indirectly taken into account), results in an expression that contains two terms of distinct natures and which, consequently, are required to be positive individually:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \dot{D}_1 = -\dot{W} + \mathbf{S} : \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \sum_{k \in E} g_{kE}^{ec} \dot{\mathcal{N}}_{kE} \geq 0 \\ \dot{D}_2 = - \sum_{k \in E} \frac{\nabla g_{kE}^{ec}}{\hat{v}_k} \cdot \mathbf{J}_{kE} \geq 0. \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

2.3.1. Electro-chemo-mechanical constitutive equation

Considering articular cartilage as a hyperelastic material, the first term $\dot{D}_1$ in Eq.(7) is considered to exactly vanish, that is

$$\dot{W} = \mathbf{S} : \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \sum_{k \in E} g_{kE}^{ec} \dot{N}_{kE}, \quad (8)$$

where $(\dot{\quad})$ denotes a time derivative, $W=W(\mathbf{E}, \mathcal{N}_{kE})$ is the internal energy per unit of initial (reference) volume V_0 , $\mathbf{S}$ is the 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, $\mathbf{E}$ is the Green-Lagrange strain tensor ($\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{I})$, where $\mathbf{F}$ is the gradient of deformation tensor) and g_{kE}^{ec} is the electro-chemical potential per unit of mole of species k .

Additionally, for the formulation of the equations that govern the tissue deformation, two constraints need to be included: the electroneutrality and incompressibility conditions. The electroneutrality condition introduces a constraint in the constitutive equation, that incrementally can be written as:

$$\dot{I}_{el} = F \sum_{k \in E} \xi_k \dot{N}_{kE} = 0, \quad (9)$$

where F is Faraday's constant ($F = 96485$ Coulomb mol⁻¹) and ξ_k is the valence of species k . The incompressibility of all the tissue constituents introduces a second constraint in the constitutive equations, that incrementally can be written as:

$$\dot{I}_{inc} = \dot{J} - \sum_{k \in E} \hat{v}_k \dot{N}_{kE} = \det \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^{-T} : \dot{\mathbf{F}} - \sum_{k \in E} \hat{v}_k \dot{N}_{kE}, \quad (10)$$

where $J = V/V_0 = \det \mathbf{F}$.

In order to satisfy the two aforementioned constraints, an augmented internal energy $\mathcal{W}$ is defined, that results from the introduction of the Lagrange multipliers ϕ_E and p_E interpreted, respectively, as the electrical potential and the pressure in the fluid EF phase

$$\mathcal{W} = W(\mathbf{E}, \mathcal{N}_{kE}) - \phi_E I_{el} + p_E I_{inc}, \quad (11)$$

from which results

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathcal{W}} &= \mathbf{S} : \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \sum_{k \in E} g_{kE}^{ec} \dot{N}_{kE} - \phi_E F \sum_{k \in E} \xi_k \dot{N}_{kE} + p_E (\det \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^{-T} : \dot{\mathbf{F}} - \sum_{k \in E} \hat{v}_k \dot{N}_{kE}) \\ &= \bar{\mathbf{S}} : \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \sum_{k \in E} \bar{g}_{kE}^{ec} \dot{N}_{kE} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{S} + p_E \det \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^{-1} : \mathbf{F}^{-T}$ and $\bar{g}_{kE}^{ec} = g_{kE}^{ec} - \hat{v}_k p_E - F \xi_k \phi_E$ are the effective 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor and the effective electro-chemical potential per unit of mole of species k , respectively.

Since $\dot{\mathcal{W}}$ is also given by

$$\dot{\mathcal{W}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}}{\partial \mathbf{E}} : \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \sum_{k \in E} \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}}{\partial N_{kE}} \dot{N}_{kE}, \quad (13)$$

the coupled electro-chemo-hyperelastic constitutive equations are obtained from $\bar{\mathbf{S}} = \partial \mathcal{W} / \partial \mathbf{E}$ and $\bar{g}_{kE}^{ec} = \partial \mathcal{W} / \partial N_{kE}$, subjected to the constraints $I_{inc} = \partial \mathcal{W} / \partial p_E = 0$ and $I_{el} = \partial \mathcal{W} / \partial \phi_E = 0$.

As in [20], the constitutive form of the energy $\mathcal{W}$ here proposed is decomposed into a coupled chemo-mechanical contribution and a purely chemical contribution, $\mathcal{W} = \mathcal{W}_{ch-mech} + \mathcal{W}_{ch}$. The coupled chemo-mechanical contribution is, in turn, decomposed into a coupled chemo-mechanical term $\mathcal{W}_{ch-mech,1}(\mathbf{E}, \mathcal{N}_{kE}) = -p_{ch}(\mathcal{N}_{kE}) (\det \mathbf{F} - 1)$ and by a product of a purely chemical term $\mathcal{W}_{ch,2}(\mathcal{N}_{kE})$ by a purely mechanical term $\mathcal{W}_{mech}(\mathbf{E})$, corresponding to the strain energy of the tissue matrix (PGs, collagen and other proteins), as

$$\mathcal{W}_{ch-mech}(\mathbf{E}, \mathcal{N}_{kE}) = \mathcal{W}_{ch-mech,1}(\mathbf{E}, \mathcal{N}_{kE}) + \mathcal{W}_{ch,2}(\mathcal{N}_{kE}) \mathcal{W}_{mech}(\mathbf{E}). \quad (14)$$

The purely chemical term is given by:

$$\mathcal{W}_{ch}(\mathcal{N}_{kE}) = RT \left(\sum_{k \in E} \mathcal{N}_{kE} \ln \mathcal{N}_{kE} - \mathcal{N}_E \ln \mathcal{N}_E \right), \quad (15)$$

where T is the temperature and R is the gas constant ($R = 8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$).

The mole based electro-chemical potentials of the species are then obtained as follows:

$$g_{kE}^{ec} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}}{\partial \mathcal{N}_{kE}} + \hat{v}_k p_E + F \xi_k \phi_E = \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}_{ch-mech}}{\partial \mathcal{N}_{kE}} + RT \ln x_{kE} + \hat{v}_k p_E + F \xi_k \phi_E, \quad (16)$$

which, in the absence of chemo-mechanical couplings ($\partial \mathcal{W}_{ch-mech} / \partial \mathcal{N}_{kE} = 0$), present their classical form, composed by a mechanical ($\hat{v}_k p_E$), a chemical ($RT \ln x_{kE}$) and an electrical ($F \xi_k \phi_E$) term.

As usual, in the definition of the electro-chemical potentials of the ionic species, only the chemical and electrical terms are retained, thus:

$$g_{kE}^{ec} = RT \ln x_{kE} + F \xi_k \phi_E, \quad k \in E^{ions}. \quad (17)$$

In the case of the electrically neutral water molecule, its electro-chemical potential, neglecting again the chemo-mechanical couplings, is defined as:

$$g_{wE}^{ec} = \hat{v}_w p_E + RT \ln x_{wE}. \quad (18)$$

The Cauchy stress tensor is also obtained as [20]:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \frac{1}{\det \mathbf{F}} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{F}^T = \frac{1}{\det \mathbf{F}} \mathbf{F} \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}_{ch-mech}}{\partial \mathbf{E}} \mathbf{F}^T - p_E \mathbf{I} = -p_{ch} \mathbf{I} + \mathcal{W}_{ch,2} \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E} - p_E \mathbf{I}, \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{F} \partial \mathcal{W}_{mech} / \partial \mathbf{E} \mathbf{F}^T / \det \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E}$. Rewriting Eq.(19), we get:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} + p_E \mathbf{I} = -p_{ch} \mathbf{I} + \mathcal{W}_{ch,2} \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E}, \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{E}$ is the 4th rank mechanical constitutive tensor of the tissue immersed in a saturated bath and $\mathbf{I}$ is the 2nd order identity tensor. In the absence of chemo-mechanical couplings ($p_{ch} = 0$ and $\mathcal{W}_{ch,2} = 1$), the classical constitutive equation of an inert porous medium is obtained, $\boldsymbol{\sigma} + p_E \mathbf{I} = \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E}$. Therefore, the first chemo-mechanical term $\mathcal{W}_{ch-mech,1}$ gives rise to an isotropic chemical stress $p_{ch} \mathbf{I}$, while the term $\mathcal{W}_{ch,2}$ is intended to amplify the stiffness of the tissue for small ionic concentrations, thus reflecting the shielding effect [6].

In order to obtain the final form of the constitutive equation, the concept of *fictitious bath* or *equilibrium bath* needs to be introduced, that is a bath whose composition and pressure $\tilde{p}_B$ may vary in time and space so that, at any time, it is in electro-chemical equilibrium with any point of the tissue. Thus, the pressure p_E can be defined as $p_E = \tilde{p}_B + \tilde{\pi}_{osm}$, where $\tilde{\pi}_{osm}$ is the osmotic (or Donnan) pressure between the tissue's point and the corresponding fictitious bath. Therefore, the constitutive equation Eq. (20) can be written as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} + \tilde{p}_B \mathbf{I} + \tilde{\pi}_{osm} \mathbf{I} + p_{ch} \mathbf{I} = \mathcal{W}_{ch,2} \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E}. \quad (21)$$

Since the properties of the fictitious bath are obtained from those of the tissue, the osmotic pressure $\tilde{\pi}_{osm}$ can be seen as a function of the primary variables and, therefore, it is eligible to enter in the constitutive equation. Due to the fact that the osmotic pressure $\tilde{\pi}_{osm}$ varies with the ionic concentration, it will be used to define both p_{ch} and $\mathcal{W}_{ch,2}$. In this sense, the following expressions are suggested in [20]:

$$p_{ch} = \alpha_p \tilde{\pi}_{osm}, \quad (22)$$

$$\mathcal{W}_{ch,2} = 1 + \alpha_w \tilde{\pi}_{osm}, \quad (23)$$

where α_p and α_w are chemo-mechanical parameters, with α_p being non-dimensional.

It is important to notice that when the composition of the tissue is uniform and the tissue is in equilibrium with an external bath of known pressure and chemical composition, $\tilde{p}_B$ and $\tilde{\pi}_{osm}$ become the real bath (p_B) and osmotic (π_{osm}) pressures (the fictitious bath then becomes the real one), and the fluid pressure at any point of the tissue is:

$$p_E = p_B + \pi_{osm} \quad (24)$$

However, when there is no equilibrium, the pressure p_E and the chemical composition are obtained, at every time, from the primary variables and never from the properties of the surrounding bath, since those properties are not constitutive, and, thus, should not be involved in the definition of the constitutive equation. The notion of *fictitious bath* is then particularly useful during transient states (e.g. when changes of the chemical composition of the bath occur) or when the external bath is inhomogeneous.

2.3.2. Generalized diffusion equation

In [18], two equivalent forms of the generalized diffusion equations, that satisfy the dissipation inequality $D_2 \geq 0$ in Eq.(7), were proposed. The first one relates the vector $\mathbf{j}$, containing the volume fluxes of the species in the fluid phase relative to the solid phase, with the vector $\mathbf{f}$ of their electro-chemical gradients by an isotropic, semi-definite positive, generalized diffusion matrix $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$:

$$\mathbf{j} = -\boldsymbol{\kappa} \mathbf{f}, \quad (25)$$

where

$$\mathbf{j} = \begin{Bmatrix} J_{wE} \\ J_{NaE} \\ J_{ClE} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f} = \begin{Bmatrix} \rho_w \nabla \mu_{wE}^{ec} \\ \rho_{Na} \nabla \mu_{NaE}^{ec} \\ \rho_{Cl} \nabla \mu_{ClE}^{ec} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \boldsymbol{\kappa} = \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_{ww} & \kappa_{wNa} & \kappa_{wCl} \\ \kappa_{Naw} & \kappa_{NaNa} & \kappa_{NaCl} \\ \kappa_{Clw} & \kappa_{ClNa} & \kappa_{ClCl} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

In Eq.(26), the electro-chemical potentials μ_{kE}^{ec} are related to the electro-chemical potentials per unit of mole by $\mu_{kE}^{ec} = g_{kE}^{ec} / \hat{n}_k$.

The second proposed form relates the vector $\mathbf{J}$, containing the volume flux of the water, the diffusive fluxes of the ionic species $\mathbf{J}_k^d = n^{kE} (\mathbf{v}_{kE} - \mathbf{v}_{wE})$ and the electrical current density within the tissue $\mathbf{I}_e$, with the vector $\mathbf{F}$, containing the gradients of the fluid pressure, of the molar fractions and of the electric potential, by a matrix $\mathbf{K}$:

$$\mathbf{J} = -\mathbf{K} \mathbf{F} \quad (27)$$

where

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{Bmatrix} J_w \\ J_{Na}^d \\ J_{Cl}^d \\ \mathbf{I}_e \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F} = \begin{Bmatrix} \nabla p_E - RT \nabla C_{PG} \\ \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_{Na}} \nabla \ln x_{NaE} \\ \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_{Cl}} \nabla \ln x_{ClE} \\ \nabla \phi_E \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (28)$$

The matrix $\mathbf{K}$ governs the coupled motions of water and ionic species inside the tissue that result from Darcy's law of seepage (due to a water pressure gradient), Fick's law of diffusion (due to an ionic concentration gradient) and Ohm's

law of electrical flow (due to an electrical potential gradient). Since the electrical current density $\mathbf{I}_e$ is a linear combination of the water volume flux $\mathbf{J}_w$ and of the ionic diffusion fluxes $\mathbf{J}_k^d$, matrix $\mathbf{K}$ is symmetric, isotropic and, at best, positive semi-definite. Its form is given in [18] by:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} k_{EE} & 0 & 0 & k_e \\ 0 & k_{NaNa}^d & 0 & k_{Nae}^d \\ 0 & 0 & k_{ClCl}^d & k_{Cle}^d \\ k_e & k_{Nae}^d & k_{Cle}^d & \sigma_e \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

where

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} k_{EE} = \frac{K_h}{\rho_w g} \text{ is the "short-circuit" permeability,} \\ K_h \text{ is the hydraulic conductivity,} \\ k_e = -k_{EE} F \tilde{e}_{PG} \text{ is the electro - osmotic coefficient,} \\ \sigma_e = n^E F \sum_{k \in E^{ions}} c_{kE} u_{kE}^* + k_{EE} F^2 \tilde{e}_{PG}^2 \text{ is the electrical conductivity,} \\ k_{kl}^d = \hat{v}_k \hat{v}_l n^E c_{kE} \frac{u_{kE}^*}{F} I_{kl} \\ k_{ke}^d = \hat{v}_k n^E c_{kE} u_{kE}^* \text{sgn}(\xi_k) \\ \tilde{e}_{PG} = e_{PG} \frac{n^E}{n^{wE}} \approx e_{PG} = \xi_{PG} c_{PG} \text{ is the fixed charge density (FCD)} \end{array} \right. \quad (30)$$

and u_{kE}^* is the effective ionic mobility of species $k \in E^{ions}$ related to the corresponding coefficient of diffusion D_{kE} by the Nernst-Einstein relation $u_{kE} = D_{kE} |\zeta_k| F/RT$, being $u_{kE}^* = \tau u_{kE}$, with τ representing the tortuosity factor.

The coefficients of the matrices $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ and $\mathbf{K}$ are related by a compatibility relation, which permits to write the coefficients of $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ as [18]:

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa} = k_{EE} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & L_{Na} & L_{Cl} \\ L_{Na} & L_{Na}^2 & L_{Na} L_{Cl} \\ L_{Cl} & L_{Na} L_{Cl} & L_{Cl}^2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & k_{NaNa}^d & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_{ClCl}^d \end{bmatrix} \quad (31)$$

where $L_k = n^{kE}/n^{wE}$, $k \in E^{ions}$.

3. Finite element formulation

3.1. Element contributions

The four field equations developed in section 2.2 that need to be satisfied are the balance of momentum, Eq.(6), the global balance of mass, Eq.(5), and the balance of mass of ions Na^+ and Cl^- , Eq.(3). From these equations the four primary unknowns of the formulation are obtained: the displacement of the solid skeleton and the electro-chemical potentials of the EF species (w , Na^+ , Cl^-). All other quantities of interest may be deduced from these four primary unknowns.

To formulate the problem in its weak form, the field equations are multiplied by virtual fields ($\delta \mathbf{u}$, $\delta \mu$), and integrated by parts over the body V , which results in:

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_V \nabla(\delta \mathbf{u}) : \boldsymbol{\sigma} \, dV &= \int_{\partial V} \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS \\
\int_V \delta \mu \operatorname{div} \mathbf{v}_S - \nabla(\delta \mu) \cdot \mathbf{J}_E \, dV &= - \int_{\partial V} \delta \mu \mathbf{J}_E \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS \\
\int_V \delta \mu \frac{dv^{kE}}{dt} - \nabla(\delta \mu) \cdot \mathbf{J}_{kE} \, dV &= - \int_{\partial V} \delta \mu \mathbf{J}_{kE} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS, \quad k \in E^{ions},
\end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is the unit outward normal to the boundary ∂V of the volume V .

The replacement of the virtual fields in Eq.(32), in each finite element, by its approximation with the shape functions $\boldsymbol{\psi}_u$ and $\boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu$ results in the non-linear first order semi-discrete equation

$$F_e^{int} = F_e^{ext}, \tag{33}$$

where F_e^{int} and F_e^{ext} are obtained by assembling the element contributions F_e^{int} and F_e^{ext} below

$$F_e^{int} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \int_{V^e} \mathbf{B}_u^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} \, dV^e \\ \int_{V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \operatorname{div} \mathbf{v}_S - \nabla \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \cdot \mathbf{J}_E \, dV^e \\ \int_{V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \frac{dv^{NaE}}{dt} - \nabla \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \cdot \mathbf{J}_{NaE} \, dV^e \\ \int_{V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \frac{dv^{ClE}}{dt} - \nabla \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \cdot \mathbf{J}_{ClE} \, dV^e \end{array} \right\} \text{ and } F_e^{ext} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \int_{\partial V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_u^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS^e \\ - \int_{\partial V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \mathbf{J}_E \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS^e \\ - \int_{\partial V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \mathbf{J}_{NaE} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS^e \\ - \int_{\partial V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \mathbf{J}_{ClE} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, dS^e \end{array} \right\}. \tag{34}$$

From the element vector of the internal forces F_e^{int} , the element stiffness and diffusion matrices may be retrieved through their definition, $K^e = \partial F_e^{int} / \partial X^e$ and $C^e = \partial F_e^{int} / \partial V^e$, with X^e and V^e representing, respectively, the vectors of the element degrees of freedom and their time derivatives:

$$X^e = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ \mu_{wE}^{ec} \\ \mu_{NaE}^{ec} \\ \mu_{ClE}^{ec} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad V^e = \dot{X}^e, \tag{35}$$

$$K^e = \begin{bmatrix} K_{uu}^e & K_{u\mu_w}^e & K_{u\mu_{Na}}^e & K_{u\mu_{Cl}}^e \\ \mathbf{0} & K_{\mu_w\mu_w}^e & K_{\mu_w\mu_{Na}}^e & K_{\mu_w\mu_{Cl}}^e \\ \mathbf{0} & K_{\mu_{Na}\mu_w}^e & K_{\mu_{Na}\mu_{Na}}^e & K_{\mu_{Na}\mu_{Cl}}^e \\ \mathbf{0} & K_{\mu_{Cl}\mu_w}^e & K_{\mu_{Cl}\mu_{Na}}^e & K_{\mu_{Cl}\mu_{Cl}}^e \end{bmatrix}, \tag{36}$$

$$C^e = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ C_{\mu_w u}^e & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ C_{\mu_{Na} u}^e & \mathbf{0} & C_{\mu_{Na}\mu_{Na}}^e & C_{\mu_{Na}\mu_{Cl}}^e \\ C_{\mu_{Cl} u}^e & \mathbf{0} & C_{\mu_{Cl}\mu_{Na}}^e & C_{\mu_{Cl}\mu_{Cl}}^e \end{bmatrix}. \tag{37}$$

The non-zero components of the matrices K^e and C^e are then:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{C}_{\mu_w u}^e &= \int_{V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \operatorname{tr} \mathbf{B}_u \, dV^e \\
\mathbf{C}_{\mu_k u}^e &= \int_{V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \frac{3}{4} \frac{v^{kE}}{n^E} z_{kE} \operatorname{tr} \mathbf{B}_u \, dV^e, \quad k \in E^{ions} \\
\mathbf{C}_{\mu_k \mu_l}^e &= \int_{V^e} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \frac{\hat{m}_l}{RT} v^{kE} z_{klE} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu \, dV^e, \quad k, l \in E^{ions},
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{K}_{uu}^e &= \int_{V^e} \mathbf{B}_u^T [(1 + \alpha_w \tilde{\pi}_{osm}) \mathbf{E} + [(R_u - \alpha_p Q_u) \mathbf{I} + \alpha_w Q_u \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E}] \otimes \mathbf{I}] \mathbf{B}_u \, dV^e \\
\mathbf{K}_{u\mu_l}^e &= \int_{V^e} \mathbf{B}_u^T [[(R_l - \alpha_p Q_l) \mathbf{I} + \alpha_w Q_l \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E}] \hat{m}_l] \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu \, dV^e, \quad l \in E^{mo} \\
\mathbf{K}_{\mu_w \mu_l}^e &= \int_{V^e} \nabla \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \rho_l \sum_{k \in E} \kappa_{kl} \nabla \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu \, dV^e, \quad l \in E^{mo} \\
\mathbf{K}_{\mu_k \mu_l}^e &= \int_{V^e} \nabla \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu^T \rho_l \kappa_{kl} \nabla \boldsymbol{\psi}_\mu \, dV^e, \quad k \in E^{ions}, l \in E^{mo},
\end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

where $\mathbf{B}_u$ is defined as the strain-displacement matrix, Q_u and Q_l are given by Eq.(A.6) and R_u and R_l are given by Eq.(B.15). To obtain each of the components of the element matrices, it is necessary to resort to the constitutive equations developed in section 2.3, taken additionally into account the manipulations described in detail in Appendix A and Appendix B.

In the finite element simulations presented in this work, a one dimensional bar element, with three nodes (quadratic interpolation) for the displacement unknown and two nodes (linear interpolation) for the electro-chemical potentials, is used. The use of two nodes and linear interpolation for the electro-chemical potentials is motivated by the fact that in classical porous media, in which the nodal degrees of freedom also comprise the water pressure, a linear interpolation is usually used to approximate this variable along the element. In this way, each variable may be approximated, within a generic element e , by the predefined shape functions multiplied by the nodal values of the respective variables: $u = [\psi_u] \{u^e\}$ and $\mu_k^{ec} = [\psi_\mu] \{\mu_k^{ec^e}\}$ with

$$u^e = \begin{Bmatrix} u^1 \\ u^2 \\ u^3 \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_k^{ec^e} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mu_k^{ec^1} \\ \mu_k^{ec^2} \end{Bmatrix}. \tag{40}$$

In order to obtain the non-zero components of the stiffness and diffusion matrices, the Gaussian quadrature rule is applied, where two integration points are used for both displacement and electro-chemical potentials.

In a 1D (uniaxial strain) analysis, the 4th rank mechanical constitutive tensor $\mathbf{E}$ defined in Eq.(20) and used in Eq.(39), involves just one constitutive parameter (E_{sat}) to be obtained from experimental results.

3.2. Time integration

For the integration of the semi-discrete equations previously developed, both an incremental and an iterative process are performed, where the steps in the incremental process are denoted by n and the iterations by i . Moreover, a midpoint scheme is used for the time integration, meaning that, for each step $n+1$, the equations are evaluated at time $t_{n+\alpha} = t_n + \alpha \Delta t$, with $\alpha = 0.5$, where $\Delta t = t_{n+1} - t_n$.

Within each step $n+1$, several iterations are performed until convergence is reached, which corresponds to a vanishing residual R :

$$R_{n+\alpha} = F^{ext}(S_{n+\alpha}) - F^{int}(X_{n+\alpha}, V_{n+\alpha}) = 0, \tag{41}$$

where S represents the nodal "loads" and X and V represent the vectors of the nodal primary variables (displacement and electro-chemical potentials) and of the nodal velocities of the primary variables, respectively. The quantities $Z = S, X, V$, evaluated at the time $t_{n+\alpha}$, are defined as $Z_{n+\alpha} = (1-\alpha) Z_n + \alpha Z_{n+1}$, with Z_n and Z_{n+1} the values of Z evaluated at time t_n and t_{n+1} , respectively.

In the present problem, the internal forces are non-linear functions of the nodal primary unknowns. In this way, a linearization of Eq.(33) around the current solution (X^i and V^i , for $i \geq 1$), through the development of the internal forces into a Taylor series neglecting the higher order terms, results in:

$$F^{ext}(S_{n+\alpha}^i) - F^{int}(X_{n+\alpha}^{i+1}, V_{n+\alpha}^{i+1}) \approx R_{n+\alpha}^{i+1} - C^*(\alpha \Delta V) = 0, \quad (42)$$

with $R_{n+\alpha}^{i+1}$ the residual at step $n+1$, evaluated at time $t_{n+\alpha}$, and at iteration $i+1$ which, recalling Eq.(41), has the form

$$R_{n+\alpha}^{i+1} = F^{ext}(S_{n+\alpha}^i) - F^{int}(X_{n+\alpha}^i, V_{n+\alpha}^i), \quad (43)$$

where $Z_{n+\alpha}^i = (1-\alpha) Z_n + \alpha Z_{n+1}^i$, with $Z = S, X, V$.

With all the above relations formulated, the iterative process is then conducted as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \text{for } i = 0 & V_{n+1}^0 = V_n, & X_{n+1}^0 = X_n + (1-\alpha)\Delta t V_n \\ \text{for } i \geq 1 & V_{n+1}^i = V_{n+1}^{i-1} + \Delta V, & X_{n+1}^i = X_n + \Delta t V_{n+1}^i = X_{n+1}^0 + \alpha \Delta t V_{n+1}^i \end{cases} \quad (44)$$

where the velocity update ΔV , in each iteration, is obtained from the linearized equation Eq.(42) where the effective diffusion matrix C^* is defined as:

$$C^* = C + \alpha \Delta t K \quad \text{with} \quad C = \frac{\partial F^{int}}{\partial V}(X_{n+\alpha}^i, V_{n+\alpha}^i), \quad K = \frac{\partial F^{int}}{\partial X}(X_{n+\alpha}^i, V_{n+\alpha}^i). \quad (45)$$

As the iterative process progresses, it is expected that the system converges until ΔV becomes sufficiently small. Thus, the convergence criterion used is the following:

$$\|\Delta \tilde{V}\|_n^i / \|\Delta \tilde{V}\|_n^0 \leq TOL, \quad (45)$$

where $\|\Delta \tilde{V}\|_n^i$ represents the norm of the normalized ΔV vector, at step n and iteration i , and TOL represents the threshold which is a very small number.

The normalization of the ΔV vector is desirable since either X and V are composed of variables (displacements, electro-chemical potentials and their time derivatives) that have different physical dimensions and orders of magnitude. In this way, the components of ΔV related to displacements are normalized by the maximum value obtained at iteration 0, and a similar normalization procedure is performed on the components of ΔV related to the electro-chemical potentials:

$$\left(\overline{\Delta V}_n^i\right)_u = \frac{(\Delta V_n^i)_u}{(\Delta V_n^0)_{max,u}} \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\overline{\Delta V}_n^i\right)_\mu = \frac{(\Delta V_n^i)_\mu}{(\Delta V_n^0)_{max,\mu}}. \quad (46)$$

Once this normalization is performed, the same threshold TOL may be used for both type of variables.

4. Conclusions

Articular cartilage is a porous medium, reinforced by collagen fibers and saturated by an aqueous electrolyte. The presence of proteoglycans (electrically charged macromolecules) is the reason why electro-chemo-mechanical interactions occur, which enhance the tissue adaptation to physiological actions.

In previous works [15,18,20], it was proposed 1) a constitutive law and 2) a generalized diffusion model for articular cartilage. In those models, the collagen fibers constitute the solid phase of the porous medium and the fluid phase is

composed by water, PGs and dissolved inorganic salts (NaCl). In the current work, two fluid compartments are also considered, in order to account for the division of water in the IF and EF spaces inside the tissue, as highlighted in [8]. However, as a new feature, the IF compartment is taken into account in a simplified way, distinct to what was previously considered in [16,17,19,20], but consistent with experimental observations [21]. This simplification avoids the definition of material parameters and functions related to the IF compartment that cannot be obtained from the existing experimental data.

A finite element program, whose formulation is based on the described model, is developed in a MATLAB environment with the purpose of numerically simulate the response of an articular cartilage sample to a combination of chemical and mechanical actions. The parametric identification and simulations of actual loading processes are described in the companion paper.

Appendix A. Osmotic equilibrium and fictitious bath

From the electro-chemical potentials of the ionic species Na^+ and Cl^- , the chemical potential of the salt NaCl may be obtained:

$$g_{NaCl} = g_{NaE}^{ec} + g_{ClE}^{ec} = RT \ln(x_{NaE}x_{ClE}), \quad (A.1)$$

with x_{kE} the molar fraction of the species k in the EF compartment.

The electroneutrality condition of the (*fictitious*) bath requires that $\tilde{x}_{ClB} = \tilde{x}_{NaB}$ (with $\tilde{x}_{ClB}$ and $\tilde{x}_{NaB}$ the molar fractions of the species in the fictitious bath), and the electroneutrality condition of the tissue imposes that $x_{ClE} = x_{NaE} + y_{PG}$ where $y_{PG} = \zeta_{PG} x_{PG} < 0$. Imposing the chemical equilibrium between the two phases (fictitious bath and cartilage tissue), $\tilde{g}_{NaCl} = g_{NaCl}$, we obtain:

$$x_{NaE}x_{ClE} = \tilde{x}_{NaB}\tilde{x}_{ClB} \quad \text{or} \quad \tilde{x}_{NaB}\tilde{x}_{ClB} = \sqrt{x_{NaE}(x_{NaE} + y_{PG})} \quad (A.2)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x}_{wB} &= 1 - \tilde{x}_{NaB} - \tilde{x}_{ClB} = 1 - 2\sqrt{x_{NaE}(x_{NaE} + y_{PG})} \\ x_{wE} &\approx 1 - x_{NaE} - x_{ClE} = 1 - 2x_{NaE} - y_{PG}. \end{aligned} \quad (A.3)$$

Note that x_{PG} is neglected in the first equality in Eq.(A.3)₂.

From the chemical equilibrium of water ($\tilde{g}_w = g_w$), the fictitious Donnan osmotic pressure is thus defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\pi}_{osm} &= p_E - \tilde{p}_B = \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} \ln\left(\frac{\tilde{x}_{wB}}{x_{wE}}\right) \approx \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} (x_{NaE} + x_{ClE} - \tilde{x}_{NaB} - \tilde{x}_{ClB}) \\ &= \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} (2x_{NaE} + y_{PG} - 2\sqrt{x_{NaE}(x_{NaE} + y_{PG})}) \end{aligned} \quad (A.4)$$

from which results $\tilde{p}_B = p_E - \tilde{\pi}_{osm}$.

In order to obtain the quantities necessary to formulate the finite element method the expression of $\tilde{\pi}_{osm}$ needs to be differentiated:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\tilde{\pi}_{osm} &\approx \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} (\delta x_{NaE} + \delta x_{ClE} - 2\delta\tilde{x}_{NaB}) \\ &= \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} (\delta x_{NaE} + \delta x_{ClE} - 2\delta\sqrt{x_{NaE}x_{ClE}}) = \sum_{k \in E^{ions}} P_k \delta x_{kE}, \end{aligned} \quad (A.5)$$

$$\text{with } P_{Na} = \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} \left(1 - \frac{x_{ClE}}{\sqrt{x_{NaE}x_{ClE}}}\right) = \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} \left(1 - \frac{x_{ClE}}{\tilde{x}_{NaB}}\right),$$

$$\text{and } P_{Cl} = \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} \left(1 - \frac{x_{NaE}}{\sqrt{x_{NaE}x_{ClE}}}\right) = \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} \left(1 - \frac{x_{NaE}}{\tilde{x}_{NaB}}\right).$$

Then, using Eq.(B.11) in Appendix B, we get:

$$\delta\tilde{\pi}_{osm} = Q_u \operatorname{div} \delta\mathbf{u} + \sum_{l \in E^{mo}} Q_l \hat{m}_l \delta\mu_{lE}^{ec},$$

$$\text{with } Q_u = \sum_{k \in E^{ions}} P_k \frac{3 y_{PG} \xi_k x_{kE}}{4 n^E}, \quad (A.6)$$

$$Q_l = \sum_{k \in E^{ions}} P_k \frac{x_{kE}}{RT} z_{kl},$$

$$z_{kl} = I_{kl} - \xi_k \xi_l x_{lE} / z_E \quad \text{and} \quad z_E = x_{NaE} + x_{ClE}.$$

As the system evolves towards the equilibrium, which occurs when the tissue is in balance with the (homogeneous) real bath (the fictitious bath then becomes the real bath), the electro-chemo-mechanical equilibrium conditions (Eq.(A.2), Eq.(A.3) and Eq.(A.4)) can also be used to obtain the equilibrium concentrations within the tissue and the osmotic pressure as a function of the known (real) bath composition $x_{NaB} = x_{ClB} = x^*$, as:

$$x_{NaE} = \frac{-y_{PG}}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{y_{PG}^2 + 4x^{*2}}}{2}, \quad x_{ClE} = \frac{y_{PG}}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{y_{PG}^2 + 4x^{*2}}}{2}, \quad (A.7)$$

$$x_{wE} = 1 - \sqrt{y_{PG}^2 + 4x^{*2}}, \quad \pi_{osm} = \frac{RT}{\hat{v}_w} \left(\sqrt{y_{PG}^2 + 4x^{*2}} - 2x^* \right).$$

By approximating the total volume of the EF phase by the volume of the EF water (water is the most abundant constituent of the EF phase of the tissue) and replacing the molar fractions by molar concentrations ($x_{kE} \approx c_{kE} \hat{v}_w$), an approximated equation for the osmotic pressure can be obtained:

$$\pi_{osm} = RT \left(\sqrt{e_{PG}^2 + 4c^{*2}} - 2c^* \right), \quad (A.8)$$

where $c^* = c_{NaB} = c_{ClB}$ is the ionic concentration of the bath.

Appendix B. Algebraic manipulations

In this Appendix some algebraic manipulations necessary to update the dependent variables and to obtain the element stiffness and diffusion matrices are provided. The constraints that must be obeyed by the molar fractions in the EF phase are:

$$\begin{cases} x_{wE} + x_{NaE} + x_{ClE} + x_{PG} = 1 \\ x_{NaE} - x_{ClE} + y_{PG} = 0, \end{cases} \quad (B.1)$$

where the PGs molar fraction x_{PG} is considered to be approximately zero. Nevertheless, the quantity $y_{PG} = \zeta_{PG} x_{PG}$ can not be neglected, since, despite the fact that x_{PG} is a very small number, the PGs valence ζ_{PG} is a very large number and, thus, y_{PG} is a significant quantity.

The volume content of the EF phase v^E is given by $v^E = V_E/V_0$, and the variation of the volume content is $\delta v^E = \delta V_E/V_0$. The volume of the EF phase is given by $V_E = \sum_{k \in E} V_{kE}$, which can be approximated by the volume of water in the EF phase V_{wE} , since water is the most abundant component in this phase. The same is true for the IF phase: $v^I = V_I/V_0 \approx V_{wI}/V_0$, and $\delta v^I = \delta V_I/V_0$. The solid phase is considered to be incompressible and thus variations of the total volume are only due to variations of the volume of the fluid phases due to exchanges of mass with the surrounding bath. In this way the following expression can be written:

$$\delta v^E + \delta v^I = \frac{\delta V_E}{V_0} + \frac{\delta V_I}{V_0} \approx \frac{\delta V_{wE}}{V_0} + \frac{\delta V_{wI}}{V_0} \quad (B.2)$$

$$= \frac{\delta V_w}{V_0} = \frac{\delta V}{V_0} = \delta \left(\frac{V}{V_0} \right) = \delta(\det \mathbf{F}) = \det \mathbf{F} \operatorname{div} \mathbf{v}_S \delta t \approx \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u}$$

Moreover, as previously mentioned, it is also defined that the variation of the volume of water in the IF and EF phases are always equal to, respectively 25% and 75% of the total variation of the volume of water: $\delta V_{wI} = 0.25 \delta V_w$ and $\delta V_{wE} = 0.75 \delta V_w$. In this way, the variation of the EF volume content is:

$$\delta v^E = \frac{3 \delta V_w}{4 V_0} = \frac{3}{4} \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

The volume fraction of the EF phase is given by $n^E = V_E/V = (\sum_{k \in E} V_{kE})/V \approx V_{wE}/V$, and the respective variation may be written as:

$$\delta n^E = \frac{\delta V_{wE}}{V} - \frac{V_{wE}}{V^2} \delta V = \frac{\delta V_{wE} V_0}{V_0 V} - n^E \frac{\delta V V_0}{V_0 V} \approx \frac{\delta V_E}{V_0} - n^E \left(\frac{\delta V_E}{V_0} + \frac{\delta V_I}{V_0} \right) = \left(\frac{3}{4} - n^E \right) \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u}. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

The variation of the PG effective molar fraction y_{PG} can be obtained considering that $y_{PG} = \xi_{PG} x_{PG} \approx \xi_{PG} N_{PG}/n^E \hat{v}_w/V$,

$$\delta y_{PG} = \xi_{PG} \delta x_{PG} \approx -\xi_{PG} \frac{N_{PG}}{(n^E)^2} \frac{\hat{v}_w}{V} \delta n^E - \xi_{PG} \frac{N_{PG}}{n^E} \frac{\hat{v}_w}{V^2} \delta V \approx -y_{PG} \left(\frac{\delta n^E}{n^E} + \frac{\delta V}{V} \right) \approx -\frac{3 y_{PG}}{4 n^E} \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u}. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

The molar fractions of the species can be defined as a function of the volume contents v^{kE} :

$$x_{kE} \approx \frac{N_{kE}}{n^E} \frac{\hat{v}_w}{V} = \frac{V_{kE}}{\hat{v}_k n^E} \frac{\hat{v}_w}{V} = \frac{\hat{v}_w v^{kE} V_0}{\hat{v}_k n^E V} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

and therefore, since $m^{kE} = \rho_k v^{kE}$,

$$\frac{\delta m^{kE}}{m^{kE}} = \rho_k \frac{\delta v^{kE}}{m^{kE}} = \frac{\delta v^{kE}}{v^{kE}} \approx \frac{\delta x_{kE}}{x_{kE}} + \frac{3}{4 n^E} \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u}, \quad k \in E^{mo}. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Using the definition of the electro-chemical potentials $\mu_{kE}^{ec} = g_{kE}^{ec}/\hat{m}_k$ and the constraints imposed to the molar fractions Eq.(B.1), the variation of the EF electrical potential can be obtained:

$$y_{PG} F \delta \phi^E = x_{wE} \hat{v}_w \delta p_E - \sum_{l \in E^{mo}} x_{lE} \hat{m}_l \delta \mu_{lE}^{ec}. \quad (\text{B.8})$$

The variation of the molar fractions of the ionic species may be also computed substituting Eq.(B.8) in the variation of the corresponding electro-chemical potentials as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta x_{kE} &= \frac{\hat{m}_k}{RT} x_{kE} \left(\delta \mu_{kE}^{ec} - \frac{\xi_k x_{wE} \hat{v}_w}{\hat{m}_k y_{PG}} \delta p_E + \frac{\xi_k}{\hat{m}_k y_{PG}} \sum_{l \in E^{mo}} x_{lE} \hat{m}_l \delta \mu_{lE}^{ec} \right) \\ &= -\frac{\xi_k x_{kE}}{RT y_{PG}} x_{wE} \hat{v}_w \delta p_E + \frac{x_{kE}}{RT} \left(\hat{m}_k \delta \mu_{kE}^{ec} + \frac{\xi_k}{y_{PG}} \sum_{l \in E^{mo}} x_{lE} \hat{m}_l \delta \mu_{lE}^{ec} \right), \quad k \in E^{ions}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Resorting once again to the electroneutrality condition $(\sum_{k \in E^{mo}} \xi_k \delta x_{kE}) + \delta y_{PG} = 0$, and using Eq.(B.5) and Eq.(B.9), the EF pressure may be defined as a function of the primary variables:

$$z_E x_{wE} \hat{v}_w \delta p_E = -\frac{3y_{PG}^2}{4n^E} RT \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u} + z_E \sum_{l \in E^{mo}} z_{lE} x_{lE} \hat{m}_l \delta \mu_{lE}^{ec}, \quad (\text{B.10})$$

where $z_E = x_{NaE} + x_{ClE}$ and $z_{lE} = 1 + \xi_l y_{PG}/z_E$.

Further manipulations may be performed in order to obtain the variations of the molar fractions of the ionic species as a function of the primary unknowns:

$$\delta x_{kE} = \frac{3y_{PG} \xi_k x_{kE}}{4n^E z_E} \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u} + \frac{x_{kE}}{RT} \sum_{l \in E^{ions}} z_{klE} \hat{m}_l \delta \mu_{lE}^{ec}, \quad k \in E^{ions}, \quad (\text{B.11})$$

where $z_{klE} = I_{kl} - \xi_k \xi_l x_{lE} z_E$ and $\mathbf{I}$, with components I_{kl} , is the identity matrix. The incremental fictitious osmotic pressure may also be defined, replacing Eq.(B.11) in Eq.(A.5).

Using Eq.(B.7) and Eq.(B.11), the mass content variations may also be defined as a function of the variations of the primary variables:

$$\delta m^{kE} = \frac{3 m^{kE}}{4 n^E} z_{kE} \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u} + \frac{m^{kE}}{RT} \sum_{l \in E^{ions}} z_{klE} \hat{m}_l \delta \mu_{lE}^{ec}, \quad k \in E^{ions}, \quad (\text{B.12})$$

from which the derivative of the volume contents of the ionic species in order of time, dv^{kE}/dt , used in Eq.(34), may be obtained:

$$\frac{dv^{kE}}{dt} = \frac{v^{kE}}{m^{kE}} \frac{dm^{kE}}{dt} = \frac{3 v^{kE} z_{kE}}{4 n^E} \operatorname{div} \left(\frac{d\mathbf{u}}{dt} \right) + \frac{v^{kE}}{RT} \sum_{l \in E^{ions}} z_{klE} \hat{m}_l \left(\frac{d\mu_{lE}^{ec}}{dt} \right), \quad k \in E^{ions}. \quad (\text{B.13})$$

The stress increment can also be computed, using the mechanical constitutive equation Eq.(21), as well as Eq.(B.10) and Eq.(A.6):

$$\delta \boldsymbol{\sigma} = -\delta p_E \mathbf{I} - \alpha_p \delta \tilde{\pi}_{osm} \mathbf{I} + (1 + \alpha_w \tilde{\pi}_{osm}) \mathbf{E} : \delta \mathbf{E} + \alpha_w \delta \tilde{\pi}_{osm} \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E}. \quad (\text{B.14})$$

Defining

$$\begin{aligned} \delta p_E &= -R_u \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u} - \sum_{l \in E^{mo}} R_l \hat{m}_l \delta \mu_{lE}^{ec} \\ \text{with } R_u &= \frac{3RTy_{PG}^2}{4n^E z_E x_{wE} \hat{v}_w}, \\ \text{and } R_l &= -\frac{z_{lE} x_{lE}}{x_{wE} \hat{v}_w}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.15})$$

Eq.(B.14) gets the form

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \boldsymbol{\sigma} &= [(1 + \alpha_w \tilde{\pi}_{osm}) \mathbf{E} + [(R_u - \alpha_p Q_u) \mathbf{I} + \alpha_w Q_u \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E}] \otimes \mathbf{I}] \operatorname{div} \delta \mathbf{u} \\ &+ \sum_{l \in E^{mo}} [(R_l - \alpha_p Q_l) \mathbf{I} + \alpha_w Q_l \mathbf{E} : \mathbf{E}] \hat{m}_l \delta \mu_{lE}^{ec}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.16})$$

In the case of a uniaxial deformation ε , Eq.(B.16) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \sigma &= \left[(1 + \alpha_w \tilde{\pi}_{osm}) E_{sat} + [(R_u - \alpha_p Q_u) + \alpha_w Q_u E_{sat} \varepsilon] \right] \frac{d(\delta u)}{dx} \\ &+ \sum_{l \in E^{mo}} [(R_l - \alpha_p Q_l) + \alpha_w Q_l E_{sat} \varepsilon] \hat{m}_l \delta \mu_{lE}^{ec}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.17})$$

References

- [1] Barbe M, Driban JB, Safadi FF, Barr AE, Popoff SN. Structure and Function of Joints. In Bone Pathology 2009 (pp. 51-60). Humana Press.
- [2] Martin RB, Burr DB, Sharkey NA, Fyhrie DP. Synovial Joint Mechanics. In Skeletal Tissue Mechanics 2015 (pp. 227-273). Springer.
- [3] Hung CT, Mow VC. Biomechanics of Articular Cartilage. In Basic Biomechanics of the Musculoskeletal System 2001 (pp. 60-101). Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.
- [4] Sophia Fox AJ, Bedi A, Rodeo SA. The basic science of articular cartilage: Structure, composition, and function. Sports Health. 2009;1(6):461–468.
- [5] Greene GW, Zappone B, Söderman O, Topgaard D, Rata G, Zeng H, Israelachvili JN. Anisotropic dynamic changes in the pore network structure, fluid diffusion and fluid flow in articular cartilage under compression. Biomaterials. 2010;31(12):3117–3128.
- [6] Eisenberg SR, Grodzinsky AJ. Swelling of articular cartilage and other connective tissues: Electromechanochemical forces. Journal of Orthopaedic Research. 1985;3(2):148–159.
- [7] Han E, Chen SS, Klisch SM, Sah RL. Contribution of proteoglycan osmotic swelling pressure to the compressive properties of articular cartilage. Biophysical Journal. 2011;101(4):916–924.
- [8] Maroudas A, Wachtel E, Grushko G, Katz E, Weinberg P. The effect of osmotic and mechanical pressures on water partitioning in articular cartilage. Biochimica et Biophysica Acta. 1991;1073(2):285–294.
- [9] Egri D, Battistella LR, Yoshinari NH. O envelhecimento da cartilagem articular. Revista Brasileira de Reumatologia. 1999;39(1):45–48.
- [10] Guilak F. Biomechanical factors in osteoarthritis. Best Practice and Research Clinical Rheumatology. 2011;25(6):815–823.
- [11] Mow VC, Kuei SC, Lai WM, Armstrong CG. Biphasic creep and stress relaxation of articular cartilage in compression: Theory and experiments. Journal of Biomechanical Engineering. 1980;102(1):73–84.
- [12] Lai WM, Hou JS, Mow VC. A triphasic theory for the swelling and deformation behaviors of articular cartilage. Journal of Biomechanical Engineering. 1991;113(3):245–258.
- [13] Gu WY, Lai WM, Mow VC. A mixture theory for charged-hydrated soft tissues containing multi-electrolytes: passive transport and swelling behaviors. Journal of Biomechanical Engineering. 1998;120:169–180.
- [14] Huyghe J. Intra-extrafibrillar mixture formulation of soft charged hydrated tissues. Journal of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics. 1999;37(3):519–536.
- [15] Loret B, Simões FMF. Articular cartilage with intra- and extrafibrillar waters: A chemo-mechanical model. Mechanics of Materials. 2004;36(5-6):515–541.
- [16] Loret B, Simões FMF. Mechanical effects of ionic replacements in articular cartilage. Part I: The constitutive model. Biomechanics and Modeling in Mechanobiology. 2005;4(2-3):63–80.
- [17] Loret B, Simões FMF. Mechanical effects of ionic replacements in articular cartilage. Part II: Simulations of successive substitutions of NaCl and CaCl₂. Biomechanics and Modeling in Mechanobiology. 2005;4(2-3):81–99.
- [18] Loret B, Simões FMF. Articular cartilage with intra- and extrafibrillar waters - mass transfer and generalized diffusion. European Journal of Mechanics, A/Solids. 2007;26(5):759–788.
- [19] Loix F, Simões FMF, Loret B. Articular cartilage with intra and extrafibrillar waters - Simulations of mechanical and chemical loadings by the finite element method. Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering. 2008;197(51-52):4840–4857.
- [20] Loret B, Simões FMF. Effects of the pH on the mechanical behavior of articular cartilage and corneal stroma. International Journal of Solids and Structures. 2010;47(17):2201–2214.
- [21] Basser PJ, Schneiderman R, Bank RA, Wachtel E, Maroudas A. Mechanical properties of the collagen network in human articular cartilage as measured by osmotic stress technique. Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics, 351(2):207–219, 1998.
- [22] Loret B, Simões FMF. Biomechanical Aspects of Soft Tissues. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 2017.
- [23] Loret B, Simões FMF. A framework for deformation, generalized diffusion, mass transfer and growth in multi-species multi-phase biological tissues. European Journal of Mechanics, A/Solids. 2005;24(5):757–781.